

Sociological Discourse on Management and Nurse Behavior at Connaught Hospital, Freetown, Western Urban, Sierra Leone

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Abstract

The sociological components in work culture have a functional social function in carving the work culture required by a hospital to determine the hospital's social value. The human social capital component will have diverse impacts and contributions on the behavior of jobholders in their employment workstation, which in turn will have an impact on the standard of social or health services delivered. This sociological inquiry intends to examine the impact of the human social capital constituent on the behavior of nurses at the Connaught Hospital, Freetown, Western Urban, Sierra Leone. This sort of sociological inquiry is a quantitative inquiry utilizing an observational consideration with a fragmentary consideration construct. The sample of this sociological inquiry is nurses who work in Connaught Hospital, as many as two hundred and seventy five nurses. The outcomes of this sociological inquiry signify that there is no reliably significant impact of person ability, inspiration, management, and the bureaucratic atmosphere on the behavior of nurses at Connaught Hospital, in diversity to task force efficiency which has a reliably relevant impact on the behavior of nurses at Connaught Hospital. It is suggested that the hospital management enhance an amicable employing condition by organizing coaching and growth in the shape of to coach individual expertise and learning. The objective is to enhance learning, expertise, and upgrade the behavior of nurses associated to the job of government jobholders in order to attain standard mercies at Connaught Hospital. Nonetheless, work culture, ability, inspiration, management, work stream, taskforce efficiency, and nurse behavior serve as a pillar in comprehending these dynamics. Heralding work culture has been considerably utilized to substitute human assets (Schulze et al, 2024). Human capital is inclusive learning, expertise, ability and owned by jobholders who will become the capital or assets of an establishment. By depending on expertise and abilities, a jobholder can manage other assets (Lee and Jo, 2023). Institutional objectives will be accomplished via the favorable behavior of its jobholders; diversely, the institution will encounter barriers in accomplishing goals when the behavior of jobholders is not efficient, in the perception that it cannot fulfill the demands of the job desired by the establishment. For bureaucratic forerunners, jobholder behavior is extremely significant because it is a criteria for triumph in supervising the institution they lead. So, behavior is a primary element for oversight's work in overseeing the institution because it is significant for oversight to identify and comprehend diverse significant aspects associated to jobholder behavior both from the causal elements and in terms of the impact element. Each of these components of Work Culture will have divergent impacts and contributions to jobholder maximization with the workstation, which in turn will have an impact on the standard of mercies provided by these jobholders whether these elements will encourage jobholders to provide better service delivery or inversely (Ringston and Matshabaphala, 2023). As one of the government health employees with a digit of

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forty to sixty percent in Sierra Leonean hospitals, nurses play a significant function in accomplishing health growth.

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Introduction

Stock of competencies or human assets has been broadly utilized to substitute work culture (). Stock of competencies is all awareness, insight, intelligence, expertise and skills owned by jobholders who will become the assets or stock of competencies of a social establishment. By depending on social proficiency, capacities, and talents a jobholder can run other asset (Arikiasamy, 2023).

Establishment objectives will be accomplished via the favorable operation of its jobholders; differently, the social establishment will encounter barriers in accomplishing objectives when the social operation of jobholders is not efficient, in the insight that it cannot encounter the demands of the job desired preferred by the establishment. For social institutional leaders, jobholder operation is very significant because it is a standard for achievement in overseeing the institution the direct. So, social operation is a focal element for oversight's job in overseeing the social institution because it is significant for oversight to identify and comprehend diverse significant components associated to jobholder operation equally from the formative elements and in terms of the impact elements.

Each of these aspects of work culture will have diverse impacts and contributions to jobholder contentment or comfort with the workstation, which in turn will have an effect on the standard of mercies or services delivered by these jobholders whether these elements will inspire jobholders to deliver better service or inversely vice versa (Ndua and Wanyioke, 2024).

As one of the health jobholders with a digit of forty to sixty percent in Freetown government hospitals, nurses play a significant social function in achieving health growth objectives. This is associated to the company of nurses on assignment or duty twenty four hours to serve patients and the figure of nurses who dominate health jobholders in Freetown hospitals. The standard of health services in Freetown government hospitals is firmly associated to the performance delivered by nurses. So that nurse performance evaluation is required regularly to evaluate the standard of accomplishing the quality of health services in Freetown government hospitals, it can nurture work fulfillment dedication, boost the confidence of the medical management field, and will eventually influence patient well-being or relief.

Nurse performance is an engagement achieved by nurses involving of performing the objectives of nursing, expressly the application of nursing management qualities itself which involve analysis, nursing diagnoses, discharge, assessment, and nursing time reports (Lucia, et al, 2022). According to Vera and Lorente (2023), assessment of nurse performance can be done by evaluating different things related to the job performed by nurses, involving the standard of job finalized, the standard of job, obligation in carrying out job, initiative and precision in job, the hurry at job. Position of freedom, behavior during job, attendance or utilize of time, connection with other staff, and experience at job.

Established on the outcomes of the assessment of the performance of the Freetown Connaught Hospital nurses, which was received from the Nursing Management Care Social Data at the Freetown Connaught Hospital, it was discovered that the average performance of the Connaught Hospital nurses was seventy one point seventy six percent, which is still meager when the sociological researcher contrast it with the relevant standards at the Connaught Hospital, which is hundred percent. Then the sociological researcher assessed and linked it with social inquiry data on nurse gratification in the outpatient ward at the Freetown Connaught hospital, which consume the theoretical premise of a questionnaire utilizing the work gratification scope of Aljumah (2023). The outcomes of a social gratification inquiry conducted in 2019 obtained data about ninety two percent of nurses being very gratified, four percent gratified, and four percent quite gratified working in hospitals. Established on the outcomes of the social inquiry, the sociological researcher advanced it via open and in-depth dialogues with various nurses in the hospital, taking into consideration employment social status, work experience, and the social space where they served, in order to discover in further detail the elements that might generate low performance nurses in this government hospital.

Established on the outcomes of previous social dialogues conducted by the sociological researcher on June 5, 2024 with various nurses working at the Connaught Hospital, Western Urban Freetown, the sociological researcher concentrated more on responses, contribution, and recommendations that might be the elements generating work displeasure gratification that could contribute to still the low average percent of the assessment of the performance of nurses in this hospital, expressly; (a) Several nurses, particularly civil servant nurses, were displeased with the salary given to them, which were often not paid on time, so nurses were less passionate in performing their jobs to the detailed; (b) Another problem is concerning the requirement of awards and disciplines that have not been executed appropriately which can impact work incentive and low work gratification of nurses and make nurses unruly or uncooperative so that the standard of performance is not ideal; (c) Moreover, the section of training that has not been impartial, upgrading or vocation track for civil servant nurses is still absent and challenging to progress, so that some nurses feel displeased with the injustice of the duties assigned; (c) That is still there by their supervisor; (d) Accessories and infrastructure for nurses are still absent, notably not providing a nurse or ward station and a comfort station in some therapeutic rooms.

Modes

Inquiry Station and Strategy

This sociological research was conducted at Freetown Connaught Hospital, Western Urban. The kind of sociological research conducted is quantitative research utilizing an observational inquiry with a cross-sectional inquiry approach.

Population and Sample

The population in this sociological inquiry were all nurses who worked at the Haji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province. The sample in this inquiry were nurses who worked at the Connaught Hospital as many as two hundred and seventy five nurses as comprising of two hundred and two on government payroll and seventy three nurses. So the total sample in this sociological inquiry was two hundred and seventy five nurses.

Mode of Gathering Social Facts

The social tool utilized in social data gathering is a questionnaire. There are five predictor modifiable that are human assets elements: individual ability, inspiration, management, the

organizational social setting, and team efficiency. The response variable is the nurse's operation. The dimension utilized in the social data rectifying procedure is to utilize a summative social scale.

Social Data Discourse

The social data discourse technique utilized is univariable sociological discourse, bivariate sociological discourse and multivariate sociological discourse with regression function social trial. Univariable social discourse was carried to acquire a review of the sociological inquiry puzzle by portraying each predictor utilized in the inquiry and the traits of the social respondents. Multidimensional sociological discourse was carried out to spot the link between dual variables, expressly between the predictor variable and response variable. The covariant sociological discourse utilized is a regression function social trial that examines one or multiple predictor variables with a response variable and spots which predictor variables are most associated to the social response variable.

Results and Discussion

Social Traits of Participants

Table one depicts the frequency social order established on the traits of the sample at the sociological inquiry site at the Connaught Hospital in Freetown, Western Urban. Traits of participants established on age the most is the age cohort of thirty to forty years as many as one hundred and forty nine social folks (fifty three point five percent). Social traits of participants established on feminine gender identity are the most participants with male social relations as many as one hundred and fifty five folks (sixty four point six percent). The social traits of participants established on years of service were predominantly female social participants with a working duration of five years, expressly one hundred and forty eight folks namely (fifty three point eight percent). Social traits of participants established on the most current learning are participants with nurses vocation as many as one hundred and thirty one folks (forty seven point six percent). Social traits of participants established on employment social status are the most participants with civil servant status as many as two hundred and two social folks (seventy three point five percent).

Table 1. Distribution of Social Participants Established on Traits of Participants at the Connaught Hospital in 2024

No.	Traits of social Participants	Overall (n)	Percentage (%)	Overall	
1.	Social Maturity	<30 Cycles	58	21	275
		30-40 Cycles	147	53.5	
		41-50 Cycles	70	25.5	
2.	Gender	Masculine	112	40,7	275
		Feminine	163	59.3	
3.	Period of Employment	1-3 Cycles	53	19.3	275
		3-5 Cycles	74	26.9	
		>5 Cycles	148	53.8	
4.	Last Training	SRN	96	34.9	275
		S1	44	16	
		S2	4	1.5	
		Nurse Vocation	131	47.6	
5.	Job rank	Bureaucrats	202	73.5	275

Univariable Sociological Discourse

Table two portrays the percentage of participants evaluation of the individual ability capability inquiry variable as much as sixty two point nine percent with individual ability categorized as exceptional and thirty seven point one percent with individual ability categorized as poor, for the individual incentive variable as much as two hundred and two, seventy three point five percent with individual incentive categorized as exceptional and twenty six .five percent with individual incentive categorized as poor, for management variables as much as eighty seven point three percent with management categorized as exceptional and twelve .seven percent with management categorized as poor, for the organizational setting variable as much as seventy seven .one percent with the organizational setting as exceptional and twenty two point nine percent with the organizational setting categorized as poor, for the team efficiency variable as much as eighty percent with team efficiency categorized as exception and twenty percent with team efficiency categorized as poor, and for the operation variable as much as sixty three point three with exceptional operation and thirty six. seven percent with categorized operation poor.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Research Variables at Haji Hospital, South Sulawesi Province

Sociological Inquiry Variable	Connaught Hospital	
	Digit	Percent
Individual Ability		
Exceptional	173	62.9
Poor	102	37.1
Individual Incentive		
Exceptional	202	73.5
Poor	73	26.5
Management		
Exceptional	240	87.3
Poor	35	12.7
Organizational Setting		
Exceptional	212	45.0
Poor	63	55.0
Team Efficiency		
Exceptional	220	80.0
Poor	55	20.0
Operation		
Exceptional	174	63.3
Poor	101	36.7

Pluridimensional Dialogue

Table three depicts the link between the predictor variable and the response variable. The outcomes of the multidimensional discourse depicted that there was no statistically relevant impact of individual ability on operation at the Connaught Hospital of Freetown, Western Urban with $p = 0.511 > 0.05$, there was no dependably relevant impact of individual incentive on operation at the Connaught Hospital of Freetown with $p\text{-value} = 0.818 > 0.05$, there is no dependably relevant impact of management on operation in FT Connaught Hospital with $p\text{-value} = 0.421 > 0.05$, there is no dependably relevant impact of the organizational setting on operation at FT Connaught Hospital with $p\text{-value} = 0.967 > 0.05$, and there is a dependably relevant impact of team efficiency on operation at the Connaught Hospital with $p = 0.024 < 0.05$.

Table 3. Comparison of Sig. to Trial Connection of Predictor Variables on Enhancing Nurse operation at Connaught Hospital, Freetown, Western Urban

Spectrums or Variables	Value of Sig.
	Connaught Hospital
Individual Ability on nurse operation	0,511
Individual Incentive on nurse operation	0,818
Management on nurse operation	0,421
The Organizational Setting on the operation of nurses	0,967
Team Efficiency on nurse operation	0,024

Multivariable Discourse

Table four analyzes how close the explicit or inexplicit impression between variables, namely between the component variables of Human Capital on the performance of nurses. The outcomes of the multivariable sociological discourse depict that the variables in the equation value Constant (Bo) = 1,440, the value of the function regression coefficient for the predictor variable individual ability (B1) = -0.056, individual incentive (B2) = -0.035, management (B3) = 0.083, the organizational setting (B4)= -0.001, and team efficiency (B5)= -0.65. The p-value of each predictor variable of individual ability is $p = 0.378$, individual incentive is $p = 0.371$, management is $p = 0.510$, the organizational setting is $p = 0.984$, and team efficiency is $p = 0.024$. By concentrating to the p-value, only the team efficiency variable has a p-value < 0.05. This means that only the team efficiency variable has an impression on operation at the Connaught Hospital, Freetown.

Table 4. Analysis of the Relationship Between Human Capital Components and Nurse Performance

Step		B	S.E	Structured Beta Weights	T	Sig.
		Classified Ability Person	-.056	.063	.056	.883
Classified Incentive Person	-.035	.068	-.032	-.511	.510	
Management Section	.083	.089	.058	.941	.348	
Section of Organizational Setting	-.001	.070	-.001	-.020	.984	
Section Efficiency	-.165	.073	-.137	2.272	.024	
Steady	1.440	.204		7.069	.000	

Discussion

Person ability is the capacity of a person to perform multiple duties in doing work or an evaluation of what a person can person. Person ability is extremely significant for jobholders because, with the capacity to ponder, evaluate, and comprehend the problems that arise, jobholders will be able to resolve all problems that arise in the establishment or institution. This sociological inquiry focused to determine how the influence of person ability from human social asset on the performance of nurses in Connaught Hospital. The researcher want to see how the influence of the person ability of nurses in performing duties and job, the capacity to ponder, evaluate, and comprehend the problems that arise, jobholders will be able to resolve all problems that arise in the institution so that it can influence the social operation of nurses. Participants in this sociological inquiry were dominated by nurses who had the person ability in an exceptional section at the

Connaught Hospital, Freetown, as many as one hundred and seventy three participants or sixty two point nine percent. Established on the outcomes of numeric discourse, it is obvious that person ability has no impact on jobholder performance at the Connaught Hospital, Freetown, Western Urban. The impact is signified by the value of $p=0.511$, owing the value of $p>\alpha = 0.511>0.05$ so that in this instance H1 is refused (Ho is approved).

Sociological inquiry from Porwal (2024) expresses that person ability has no impact on auditor social performance. This is because the auditor only follows the regulatory procedures in the KAP without further deepening his knowledge and work.

This is contradictory with inquiry from Gonzalez (2021), which expresses that the Person Ability variable has an important threshold or level of t sig. $(0.000) < (0.05)$. This means that relatively the Person Ability variable at job has an important impact on jobholder performance. Established on these outcomes, the second assumptions for the Person Ability Individual variable at job in the inquiry that has been done in this case is social creditworthy (Ho is declined and Ha is approved). This means that Person Ability variable at job considerably impacts jobholder performance or operation.

Social inquiry from Angeles Lopez-Carbarcos (2021) expresses that person ability considerably impacts knowledge, attitude, and practice performance. The higher the person ability owned by the jobholder, the higher the capability to enhance its institutional performance or operation.

Inquiry carried out by Shatz (2024) utilizing t-test discourse (bias) depicts that the value for the person ability variable is 7.520 (exceeding the maximum of 1.684), which indicates or implies it has an impression on knowledge, attitude and practice.

Sociological inquiry from Alkassab (2022) states that established on the outcomes of the t-test of the person ability variable (X1), a relevant value of sig t $(0.045) \leq 0.05$ is acquired so that the person individual ability variable has a relevant impression on the hospital's non-commercial operation. The expressive discourse in this inquiry depicts that the ordinary response to the items on the person ability variable is in the exceptional section with an impressive mean value of four point thirty seven percent.

Impression of Person Incentive on the Performance of Nurses

Rokhayati et al (2024) explains that Incentive is the acceptance to spend a lofty threshold or level of energy for organizational objective, which is suctioned by the capability of that energy to meet some person demands. In this instance, the demand is an internal state that generates certain results to look appealing. Asanaka et al (2023) portrays incentive as the inaugural and order of behavior, and knowledge incentive is certainly a behavioral lecture.

Another element that can also impact jobholder performance or operation is jobholder incentive. Zhao and Van de Walle (2024) define incentive as procedures that assist regulate the enthusiasm, path, and endurance of persons in an effort to accomplish objectives. Incentive is a procedure that commence from a physical and cognitive social power or demands that results in social behavior or motivation focused at an objective or motivation.

This sociological inquiry focused to discover how the influence of person incentive from human asset on the performance of nurses in Connaught Hospital. The researcher determine to discover how the influence of dynamic social elements and motivation that can activate a perception of social intensity and is also capable to transform human social behavior or persons to arrive at things that are exceptional for them so that they can affect the social operation or performance of nurses.

Participants in this sociological inquiry were dominated by nurses who had person incentive individual with exceptional sections in the Connaught Hospital, Freetown, Western Urban, as many as two hundred and two participants or seventy three percent.

Established on the numerical sociological discourse outcomes, it is acknowledged that person incentive has no consequence on jobholder performance at the Connaught Hospital, Freetown. The effect is depicted by the value of $p = 0.818$, because the value of $p > 0.818 > 0.05$ so that in this instance H_1 is declined (H_0 is approved).

This sociological outcome is in line with Adinugraha and Adib (2023) inquiry, which depicts that person incentive relatively or partly, does not have a relevant impact on auditor social performance. This is owing to the lack of person incentive and not being high enough to inspire social auditors to accomplish high social performance. This outcome refutes the inquiry outcomes of Al-Zahrani and Al-Harbi (2023) and Al-kandi et al (2023) that person incentive relatively or partly impacts the performance of social auditors or jobholders.

The outcome of Lansanthi's inquiry (2023) depicts that person incentive relatively or partly does not significantly impact social auditor operation or performance. This is owing to the lack of person incentive and not being high enough to inspire social auditors to accomplish high social performance. This outcome result refutes the outcomes of social inquiry by Christensen (2022) and Larbi (2024) that person incentive relatively or partly impacts the performance of social auditors or jobholders.

Established on social inquiry from Chatzi (2024) states that the coefficient table depicts that the t-count value is lesser than the t-table, expressly $1.101 < 2.055$ with a relevant threshold of $0.281 > 0.05$, which means Hypothesis H_a is declined and H_0 is approved, so person incentive has no favorable and important to jobholder social performance.

This outcome is not in line with social inquiry from Hao (2023), which states that the person incentive variable (X_2) has a relevance value of $\text{sig } t (0.033) < = 0.05$, so that the person incentive variable has a relevant impression on the social institution's non-commercial social operation. The outcomes of inquiry carried out by Gao and He (2023), states that capability and incentive have a favorable impact on social operation.

Impression of Management on the Performance of Nurses

Management is a craft, social role, procedure, and capability to impress and lead folks via compliance, task, and commitment to achieve something in line with the aims purposes that have been position.

Management in nursing is the capability and expertise of a nurse manager in impressing other nurses under their oversight to perform their duties and tasks in delivering nursing mercies or services and care so that nursing objective are accomplished. Every manager has diverse potential in management, but this expertise can be acquired so that management capabilities can always be enhanced or upgraded.

This sociological inquiry focused to discover how the influence of management from human social asset on the social performance of nurses in Connaught Hospital. The sociological researcher wants to examine how the influence of managers in pursuing jobholder involvement in an effort to accomplish organizational social objectives goals can impact the social performance of nurses.

Participants or respondents in this sociological inquiry were dominated by nurses who had exceptional management in the Connaught Hospital, Freetown, Western Urban, as many as two hundred and forty participants or respondents or eighty seven point three percent. Established on the outcomes of numerical discourse, it is known that management has no impact on jobholder social performance or operation at the Connaught Hospital, Freetown, Western Urban. The impact is signified by the value of $p = 0.818$, because the value of $p > \alpha = 0.421 > 0.05$, so in this instance, H_1 is declined (H_0 is approved).

Established on the outcomes of sociological inquiry from Chatzi (2024) expressed that established on the test outcomes, it is familiar that the coefficient table depicts that the t-count value is lesser than the t-table, expressly $1.229 < 2.055$ with a relevance threshold of $0.281 > 0.05$, which interprets Hypothesis H_a is declined and H_0 is approved, then management does not have a favorable and relevant impact on jobholder social operation. This interprets that the management in the section at Connaught Hospital Bank is still less efficient in socially constructing the human social asset of its jobholders.

This outcome is not in line with the sociological inquiry of Maley et al (2024), which is in accordance with the inquiry of Awan et al (2020) and the social inquiry of Gu and Luo (2022) that management mode has a straight impact on social auditor operation or performance. The outcomes of this sociological inquiry signify that the management mode in knowledge, attitude and practice is the predominant element in considering and composing the trait of the social entity or reality. Furthermore, the trait of the reality or entity will impact the result of the social auditor's operation.

Sociological inquiry from Weerakon (2023) expressed that the outcomes of the management variable t-test (X5) acquired a relevance value of $\text{sig } t (0.049) < = 0.05$ so that the management variable has an important impression on the social institution's non-commercial operation.

The Impression of Organizational Setting on the Performance of Nurses

The impression of organizational setting on organizational behavior can be favorable or unfavorable; for instance, the connection between seniors and juniors is less cordial, a strict bureaucracy can direct to unfavorable characters, high job pressure, and low incentive and work gratification. This organizational setting will establish low organizational associate operation. On the other hand, if jobholders work in a pleasant and neat space, a conducive senior and junior social connection and a relaxed institutional bureaucracy will direct to a favorable conduct, low job pressure, and high incentive and work gratification. Subsequently, high jobholder operation will be established. Organizational setting is the central pillar that influences jobholder behavior in accomplishing organizational operation.

Discourse of the Impact of Human Social Asset on Nurse Engagement

The intent of this sociological inquiry was to determine the impact of the organizational setting on the operation of nurses. The sociological researcher want to perceive how the impression of the organizational setting on jobholder operation at job. The prevalence of favorable organizational aid is associated to social welfare at job resulting in a rigid perception of passion and devotion to job in delivering mercies to patients.

Established on the outcomes of numerical discourse, it is obvious that the organizational setting has an impact on the operation or performance of nurses at the Connaught Hospital, Freetown, Western Urban. The impact is depicted by the value of $p = 0.967$, because the value of $p < \alpha = 0.967 < 0.05$ so that in this instance, H_1 is declined (H_0 is approved).

The outcomes of this sociological inquiry are not significant to the inquiry of Albert (2024), Udayanga (2024), which proves that organizational setting has an important impact on social operation. In Albert's inquiry, he perceives that the organizational setting partly has a straight impact on jobholder social operation, where the organizational setting is one of the elements that impact social operation.

Bangura (2023) also established or confirms that organizational setting impacts social operation. Bangura (2023) attempted to examine the social operation of jobholders at Fourah Bay College Library, and the outcomes depicted that organizational social setting climate could impact operation, where the outcomes of this finding are that organizational setting and social operation have an extremely robust social connection and impression.

The outcomes of this sociological inquiry also evaluate the theory of that organizational social setting is interpreted as a set of traits of the job community that is sensed openly or indirectly by jobholders and are thought to have an impact on their job behavior. Organizational setting connects to duplicative behavior patterns that are demonstrated in the regular social community of the institution, as persons observe, comprehend, and define within the institution.

Impact of Team Efficiency on the Performance of Nurses

The efficiency of the team is the accomplishment of organizational objectives in line with the set social moment. In Cottage Hospital, for instance, in the nursing section, individual capabilities, incentive, management, organizational setting, team efficiency are also extremely significant to accomplish social objectives with the moment stated in line with hospital social policy.

The intent of this sociological inquiry is to sense how the impact of team efficiency on the social operation of nurses. The sociological researcher intend to perceive how person capabilities, incentive management, organizational social setting, team efficiency on jobholders towards their job. The prevalence of favorable team efficiency is associated to welfare at job so that a roust perception of commitment and passion to work emerges in delivering mercies or services to patients so that it can impact the social operation of jobholders.

Established on the outcomes numerical discourse, it is known that there is an impact team of team efficiency on jobholder social operation at Connaught Hospital, Freetown, Sierra Leone. The impact is depicted by the value of $p = 0.024$, because the value of $p < \alpha = 0.024 < 0.05$ so that in this instance, H1 is approved (Ho is declined).

These outcomes are in accordance with Chatzi's inquiry (2024) which depicts that established on the outcomes of the t-test of the team efficiency (X4) variable, it is earned that the importance value of sig t (0.937) ≥ 0.05 so that the team efficiency variable has an irrelevant impact on the social institution's non-commercial social operation.

This is in accordance with Kim and Ko (2023) inquiry, which utilizes the team efficiency variable and depicts favorable and irrelevant outcomes. This is owing to the social fact that team efficiency has not yet been designed, which may not be influenced by elements of organizational social context, system, approach, and reward social structure to enhance auditor performance so that it cannot enhance auditor operation.

This sociological inquiry is not relevant to Nnko (2024) which depicts that partly the team efficiency variable has no relevant impact on the social institution's non-commercial operation in advertising nursing institutions registered with the Sierra Leone National Council for Technical, Vocational, and Other Awards. This is demonstrable by the outcomes of the estimation of the social importance of the social institution's non-commercial operation variable t of 0.937 or > 0.05 .

According to the outcomes of Ayasreh's inquiry (2022), team efficiency partly or relatively has no important impact on social auditor operation. The outcomes of Ayasreh's inquiry (2022) are in accordance with the outcomes of Nnko's inquiry research (2024). This is owing to the evidence that team efficiency has not yet been designed, which may not be influenced by elements of organizational social context, structure, approach, and reward structure to improve social auditor operation so that it cannot improve auditor social operation. The outcomes of Albert's inquiry (2024) discovered that both partly and simultaneously, all human capital elements made an actual contribution to the social operation of auditors in terms of knowledge, attitude and nursing practice.

Conclusion

This sociological inquiry concludes that there is no impact of person ability on nurse social operation, no impression of person incentive on nurse operation or performance, no impression of management on nurse social operation, no influence of the organizational social setting on nurse performance, and no impact on team efficiency on nurse social behavior or performance. Established on the outcomes of the sociological inquiry and the judgments that have been developed, several proposals or suggestions are offered as thus; the hospital should be able to concentrate to the areas of work of jobholders who have individual capacity, increase jobholder incentive in the shape of recognition, self-actualization, physical, social, security, enhancing management ability has a link with the design of jobholder social operation by, and increasing a cordial job setting, by conducting training and growth development in the shape of training and education.

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